

OCEAN ICE News – July 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to July's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, OCEAN ICE at UN Ocean Decade Conference, highlighting June's Climate Coffee and a recent OCEAN ICE publication. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in August, September, October and November. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in August!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Kateryna Terletska

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Kateryna Terletska, a researcher within OCEAN ICE.

Read the feature on Kateryna [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at UN Ocean Decade Conference

Andrew Meijers and Gael Durand represented the OCEAN ICE and PROTECT project at the third United Nations Ocean Convention in Nice over June 9-13th. They delivered presentations and sat in panel discussions in the INSPIRE area of the EU Digital Ocean Pavilion —hosted at "The Whale" within the UNOC3 green zone on the 11th of June.

The Rising Sea Levels session, attended by domain experts, policymakers and the public, highlighted the issues presented to Europe and the world via rising sea levels, as well as scientific and policy advances in addressing them.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Webinar Series

The OCEAN ICE webinar series, hosted by the European Polar Board, is set to continue! The webinars offer insights into the OCEAN ICE project, showcasing ongoing research, key findings, and expected outcomes from various work packages.

On the 13th of May, EPB presented a webinar for WP4 on Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes, here's a summary on what the webinar covered:

This is the fourth webinar in the series introducing the OCEAN:ICE project. In this session, we explore Work Package 4 (WP4), which focuses on quantifying deep uncertainty in the Antarctic ice sheet and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing, which is one of the key focuses of the project.. This webinar features talks by:

- Jan De Rydt (Northumbria University) - Introduction to Work Package 4)
- Vio Coulon (Université Libre de Bruxelles) - Future Freshwater Fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet
- Qing Qin (Northumbria University) - Calibration of Ice-Sheet Melt Parameterizations
- Frank Pattyn (Université Libre de Bruxelles) - Deep Uncertainty in Freshwater Fluxes

The webinar concludes with a public Q&A session.

Catch up on the webinar here: [OCEAN ICE WP4 Webinar - Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under Climate forcing](#)

Don't miss out - join the conversation and stay informed about the latest developments of the project.

OCEAN:ICE **EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD**

OCEAN ICE WP4 WEBINAR

QUANTIFICATION OF ANTARCTIC ICE SHEET DEEP UNCERTAINTY AND FRESHWATER FLUXES UNDER CLIMATE FORCING

This webinar will be the fourth in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

**13 May 2025
10:30 CEST**

© Dr. Renuka Bache

Funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – June

Catch up on June's Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino: Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, Drawing on OCEAN ICE experience [here](#).

What this webinar is about: The Horizon Europe-funded project OCEAN ICE adheres to open science practices and supports the publication of complementary materials that facilitate the reuse of the project's data. One key tool is the OCEAN ICE literacy portal, which provides instructions and examples about creating new research products using Jupyter Notebooks, which are openly available for testing and further use. In this talk, after a short introduction about how to interact with OCEAN ICE's data service (ERDDAP) using Python, the participants will be guided through the exploration of these data and their visualization in a Jupyter environment. In this way, the participants will obtain the tools to play with code using the same data typology that is used in the Notebooks available in open access for the OCEAN ICE project.

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Pietro Viglino (ETT)

Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project

Danish Meteorological Institute

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OCEAN ICE Publication - Current reversal leads to regime change in the Amery Ice Shelf cavity in the 21st century

A paper featuring members from OCEAN ICE, including Jing Jin and Tony Payne was published recently. Please find a short summary of the paper below.

The Amery Ice Shelf cavity is one of the largest cold cavities filled by relatively cold Dense Shelf Water. However, in this study, we show that warm intrusion of modified Circumpolar Deep Water flushes the Amery cavity, which changes it from a cold cavity to a warm cavity and leads to an abrupt increase in the basal melt rate in the 2060s. The shift to a warm cavity is attributed to a freshening-driven current reversal in front of the ice shelf.

Read the full paper [here](#).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

OCEAN ICE Deliverables and Milestones submitted

The OCEAN ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- D1.8 '[Model-based quantification of fluxes between shelf seas](#)'
- M29 '[Float deployment and data delivery to the community via ARGO servers](#)'
- D3.1 '[Contribution of continental scale ice dynamics processes to freshwater fluxes](#)'

The progress and results of OCEAN ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in September, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Amina Ben Salah on A Copula-Based Approach to Explore Climate-Driven Ocean Variability In the Gibraltar Strait.

28 August 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

28 August 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Amina Ben Salah (UAE)

**A Copula-Based Approach to Explore
Climate-Driven Ocean Variability in the
Strait of Gibraltar**

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Climate Coffee with Audrey Miniere on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

25 September 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Climate Coffee

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

Estimating ocean warming: challenges and recommendations for robust assessment

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean MHW

30 October 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Climate Coffee

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Natacha Legrix De La Salle on Surface and Subsurface Compound MHW and Biogeochemical Extremes

Under Climate Change.

27 November 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Climate Coffee

27 November 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

**Natacha Legrix De La Salle (Univ.
Liverpool)**

**Surface and Subsurface Compound
Marine Heatwave and Biogeochemical
Extremes Under Climate Change**

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 20-25 July 2025, [Busan IAMAS-IACS-IAPSO Joint Assembly 2025 \(JMCP20\)](#), the Republic of Korea
- 15-17th September 2025, OCEAN ICE Annual Project meeting, Copenhagen, Denmark

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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UK Research
and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452.